

Investigating the potential of Blockchain to enhance Customer Data Privacy in the Banking Sector of Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Technological innovations of the world have profoundly influenced business operations, enhancing efficiency across industries. As a result, banks and financial institutions have prioritized research and development to identify new business models that streamline processes, optimize operations, and safeguard data. However, current data privacy applications and measures face various threats and challenges stemming from technological, economic, and social factors, as highlighted by previous research. This has significantly affected the industries such as the Banking sector which act as the financial intermediates to secure a society's economy. Blockchain technology has emerged promising in the modern technological era as a technology that is capable of transforming business processes, with special regard to safeguarding the sensitive and confidential data of any business. This research study aims to explore the capability that Blockchain technology holds to enhance customer data privacy in the Banking sector of Sri Lanka. Qualitative data collection method was performed with in-depth, one-on-one virtual interviews conducted with industry experts with knowledge of the Blockchain and Fintech realm. The research identified nine key themes addressing the research questions. Data privacy and protection measures are hindered by low awareness of data protection. Weaknesses in technological alignment and organizational infrastructure leads to data protection vulnerabilities and diminished customer trust. Conversely, Blockchain technology holds attributes with potential benefits for the banking sector, particularly in enhancing data privacy and improving customer satisfaction. However, various challenges could impede its implementation are present. The study also explored strategic directions for effectively incorporating Blockchain to achieve organizational objectives. This study provides valuable insights to Sri Lankan Banking industry stakeholders aiming to leverage Blockchain to enhance their operations to become the industry leaders in innovation and providing efficient financial services. Also, this helps anyone interested in integrating Blockchain to enable more secure transactions between business units.

Keywords: *Blockchain, Banking sector, Privacy, Data protection*